

IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF BIO-INSPIRED KAGOME SANDWICH CORE STRUCTURES MANUFACTURED THROUGH SELECTIVE LASER MELTING

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ABSTRACT

Additive manufacture of titanium structures allows the realisation of advanced design strategies not achievable through traditional manufacturing methods. This work analyses the performance of bio-inspired 3D Ti-6Al-4V Kagome truss core structures produced by selective laser melting for composite sandwich structures. Mechanical testing is conducted in static (compression/shear) testing to determine the structural behaviour and energy absorption characteristics. A finite element model validates the structural performance and failure of the static tests and is utilized to assess the dynamic (impact) performance. The results are benchmarked against commonly used core structures such as honeycomb and foam cores through the use of design charts. The presented results show that the high compressive strength of 3D Kagome truss structures results in superior impact performance when considering the elastic impact energy threshold and crush energy limit of the core.

1 INTRODUCTION

Metallic core designs for sandwich structures play an important structural role in high performance light-weight structural applications for aerospace and automotive structures. In recent years, the advancement of metallic additive manufacturing technologies has led to the exploration of alternative 3D core designs for composite sandwich structures.

Energy absorption behaviour of structures is deemed important in various structural applications for improved crash worthiness, armouring protection, bird strike, and tool drop incidents [1,2]. The core inside sandwich structures can play important role to resist the incidental impact on the structure by deforming elastically or permanently.

In this research Ti-6Al-4V Kagome structures produced by Selective Laser Melting (SLM) are evaluated for their impact behaviour and energy absorbance capacity and compared to standard core materials. Kagome truss geometries are a special class of bio-inspired 3D trusses. The compressive strength of Kagome titanium lattice structures has been shown to outperform commercial core materials. The static energy absorbance is similar or superior to honeycomb structures, depending on the parameters (internal angle, strut thickness) of the Kagome structures. This translates into an impact performance with significantly reduced permanent deformation while maintaining similar energy absorbance.

2 DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING

The SLM equipment used in this work is a SLM250HL operated under Argon to avoid material oxidation. Kagome truss structures with a height of 11mm, internal angles of 55 and 60° and various truss diameters ranging from 0.5 to 1.2mm are manufactured with attached titanium skins. Incorporation for the metallic face skins is required for the discrete core element arrangement for the purpose of structural testing and improved surface attachment of composite skins with high stiffness and strength. The build direction is upward as indicated in Figure 1 to allow for structural build without additional support structures. This was discussed in detail in related work by the authors [3].

Figure 1: SLM build direction of Kagome structures with attached face sheets (from [3]).

The SLM build parameters are given in Table 1. These parameters were evaluated to result in minimal porosity for the manufactured components.

Parameter		Value
Laser power	W	175
Layer thickness	μm	30
Area scan speed	mm/s	710
Energy density	J/mm^3	68.5
Hatch type		Checkerboard
Hatch spacing	μm	120
Spot size	μm	80
Platform temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	200

Table 1: SLM build parameters.

3 MECHANICAL TESTING

Static compression and shear testing was undertaken to determine the strength and failure characteristics of 3D Kagome structures for various angles and diameters. Accurate displacement and strain values were measured through an attached extensometer (compression) and LVDT (shear). The test set-up can be seen in detail in a related reference by Ullah et al [3]. All specimens were loaded with displacement control of 0.5mm per minute; and the tests were stopped once prominent failure was observed.

Force and displacement were recorded for each compression and shear test. To obtain results for strength and moduli for shear and compression loading, the following data analysis was undertaken:

$$\sigma_{\max} = F_{\max} / A_{\text{face}} \quad (1)$$

$$E = \sigma / \varepsilon \quad \text{with} \quad \varepsilon = \Delta h / h, \quad (2)$$

where A_{face} represents the top or bottom face area of the unit cell element.

Volumetric energy, i.e. the energy per unit volume, is used as a measure of energy absorbance and

is determined from the integral of the stress-strain curve until the point of structural failure:

$$E_v = \int_0^{\varepsilon_f} \sigma d\varepsilon, \quad (3)$$

where ε_f is the failure strain of the structure. The gravimetric energy, which is a measure of energy absorbed in the structure per unit mass, can then mathematically be written as:

$$E_g = E_v / \rho \quad (4)$$

where ρ is the density of the structure.

Impact testing at various impact energies can be undertaken. A cylindrical impactor head with 10mm diameter is chosen to impact on-centre and off-centre with regard to the location of the Kagome trusses within the panel. The weight of the impactor is 365 grams. Force during impact, inbound velocity and acceleration are measured during the test. Various impact scenarios may be determined by changing the impact energy level, such as the elastic energy limit, barely visible damage energy limit and crush energy limit.

Figure 2: Impact test rig for structures

4 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

An explicit FE model in Abaqus 6.12 with nonlinear material and geometry was used for the numerical simulations. An elastic-plastic model with ductile fracture and progressive damage was defined for Ti-6Al-4V. The truss members were modelled with tetrahedral elements (C3D4) on the outer surface and triangular prism (C3D6) and brick (C3D8R) elements at the centre of the truss cross-section with elements size 0.13 to 0.15mm. This mesh specification is used in compression and shear models in trusses. The maximum value of 99 % degradation is chosen to delete an element from the mesh.

The elastic-plastic model for Ti-6Al-4V is used to define the elastic and plastic hardening behaviour (see Figure 3(a)), while failure of the material is modelled through a ductile damage criterion. The failure of ductile metals is strongly dependent on the stress triaxiality as established by previous research studies [4,5] and the failure strain envelope for SLM built structures from Ti-6Al-4V was determined by Ullah et al. [3]. Figure 3(b) shows the dependence of failure strain on the stress triaxiality. It can be seen that the failure strain in SLM-build Ti64 is lower for the whole triaxial stress range due to the more martensitic microstructure [6].

Figure 3: (a) Dependence of failure strain on stress triaxiality and (b) predicted tensile failure (from [3])

The parameters in Table 2 were evaluated by Ullah et al [3] for the SLM microstructure according to Figure 3(b):

Parameter	Value
D_1	0.1
D_2	0.1
D_3	1.3
D_4	-0.03
D_5	0.2
D_6	1.15
D_7	2.0
η_T	0.458

Table 2: Ductile failure mode parameters.

For the static tests, a time period of 0.05s for around 50% strain in compression and shear was utilized with semiautomatic mass scaling with a stable time control of $1e-7$ s. Viscous damping was introduced in the system to lessen the effect of unwanted vibration for the breaking structure. A value of $4.3e-4$ MPa s was used for the viscosity coefficient, which is around 2% of the product of wave speed and density of the titanium.

For impact conditions, simulations of deformation and damage were undertaken for a range of impact energies (2.5 to 5.0 J) for both Kagome and honeycomb core structures. The structural damage as a function of impact energy was determined. Semi-automatic mass scaling is used with minimum time increment of $5e-8$ s, while the total time step is up to 5ms to cover the impact event.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Under compressive loading, the peak load and the elastic stiffness correlate well with FE simulation and mechanical tests as seen in Figure 4(a) for a Kagome structure with uniform truss diameter of 1.2mm and internal angle of 55° . As well-established for truss structures, the stress-strain curves initially exhibited a linear elastic slope allowing for evaluation of respective compressive stiffness. The point of peak load corresponds to critical bending of truss members (onset of plastic buckling) followed by truss failure in the region of highest bending stress, which is correctly predicted through the failure model. Figure 4(b) shows the correlating Ashby design chart for compression, indicating superior performance of Kagome structures compared to conventional core materials and structures.

Figure 4: (a) Compressive loading with numerical prediction for Kagome structures with diameter of 1.2mm and internal angle of 55° and (b) compressive strength design chart

Under shear loading the structural failure behaviour is more complex as there are two cells involved in the shear test set-up and there is consequently more than one location of failure (see Figure 5(a)). The first load drop represents the total failure of one cell and is considered as failure of structure for the calculation of energy absorbance. Figure 5(b) shows again the superior shear strength of Kagome structures when compared to traditional foam and honeycomb core materials. It should be noted that values from shear tests are divided by factor two for the design charts to account for the fact that two cells were tested.

Figure 5: (a) Shear loading with numerical prediction for Kagome structures with diameter of 1.2mm and internal angle of 55° and (b) shear strength design chart

The gravimetric energy during static testing is compared in Figure 6(a) for compression and in Figure 6(b) for shear. Less design chart information is available for shear, but it can still be seen that Kagome structures are situated amongst the structures with the lowest density properties. For compression, Kagome structures with lowest angle and largest thickness perform best; while for shear, lower diameter struts result in the lowest density and highest energy uptake during failure.

Figure 6: Gravimetric energy under (a) compression and (b) shear loading as determined from evaluated literature data and Eq. (4).

It should be noted that Kagome structures do not significantly outperform the benchmarked aluminium honeycomb structure for energy absorption as in the case of compression and shear strength. This is due to the failure characteristics of honeycomb cell walls during deformation, which result in self-similar buckling behaviour along the length of the cell wall at nearly constant load. Interestingly, this characteristic difference in static behaviour also results in very different impact behaviour.

Figure 7 shows the comparison of the predicted finite element analysis and experimental test results for an impact energy of 2.9J on a honeycomb structure of initially 11mm height. The force-time history curve is predicted well, and good agreement is also achieved for the permanent deformation after impact.

Figure 7: Comparison of impact behaviour of a representative aluminium honeycomb structure (foil thickness = 0.04 mm, skin thickness = 1 mm) with 2.9 ± 0.1 J impact energy (drop height = 800mm, inbound velocity = 3.75 ± 0.08 m/s)

Figure 8(a) compares the force-displacement characteristics for both Kagome and honeycomb structures during impact. For the same impact energy, the significantly higher strength of Kagome structures translates into a much higher maximum force and much shorter duration of impact. In each of the neighbouring Kagome structures, one of the struts has broken in a symmetric fashion around the point of impact (see Figure 8(b)). The honeycomb structures on the other hand is crushed (permanently deformed) by a significant amount; resulting in a much lower maximum impact force

and much longer impact contact duration. The resulting deformation is shown in Figure 8(c). Interestingly, the total energy uptake (area under the curve) during the impact event is similar as indicated initially by the static energy adsorption design charts.

Figure 8: Comparison of impact behaviour of Kagome with strut diameter of 0.8mm and aluminium honeycomb structures (foil thickness=0.04 mm) for an impact energy of 3.73 Joules with a) simulated force-displacement curves during impact, b) impact failure of Kagome structure and c) impact failure of honeycomb structure.

Table 3 summarizes some of the numerical outcomes of the current analysis. The higher compressive strength translates into a higher impact energy threshold for initial failure and significantly lower permanent deflection of the core. It is speculated that the minimised deformation of the core is also beneficial in preventing delamination damage within attached composite face skins. This will be further investigated. Further experimental work will also focus on the influence of advanced bio-inspired metal/composite interface features to suppress critical delamination damage.

Parameter	Kagome	Al Honeycomb
Elastic energy limit [J]	0.12	0.0005
Barely visible energy limit (0.5mm permanent deformation) [J]	1.8	0.183
Crush limit (10mm permanent deformation) [J]	17.1	3.7

Table 3: Summary of numerical impact test results

6 CONCLUSIONS

Kagome structures as manufactured through selective laser melting have shown to possess superior static strength properties under compression and shear loading. Their energy absorption in static failure is similar to aluminium honeycomb materials.

During impact events, this translates into a significantly higher threshold for the elastic energy limit, barely visible energy limit and crush limit. The energy absorption is similar for the two types of structures despite significantly different deformation characteristics. However, it is speculated that the significantly reduced permanent deformation for Kagome structures for the same impact energy is beneficial in suppressing composite skin delamination and core/interface delamination.

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